

wh i s p e r s

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HYPERCOMP
Hyperspectral Computing Laboratory

Spectral Unmixing of Hyperspectral Data

Antonio J. Plaza

Hyperspectral Computing Laboratory (HyperComp)
Dept. Technology of Computers & Communications, University of Extremadura
E-mail: aplaza@unex.es
URL: <http://www.umbc.edu/rssipl/people/aplaza>

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The Concept of Hyperspectral Imaging

“Imaging Spectroscopy (hyperspectral remote sensing) deals with data from instruments acquiring reflectance images in a large (>40) number of narrow (<0.01 to 0.02 μm . in width), contiguous (i.e., adjacent) spectral bands allowing to derive the mineralogy of objects or obtaining information on soil, water and biochemical composition.”

Alexander F. H. Goetz, IGARSS 2006

“The challenge of mapping minerals on any moon or planet with hyperspectral imaging relies on sub-pixel characterization of spectral features from thousands of possibilities.”

Lesson (not learned): The advantage of the concept (of imaging spectrometry) is that no more committees need to be formed to develop a rationale for particular spectral bands and to compromise among disciplines when it comes time to build the sensor’ [Goetz, 1992]

Levels of Spectral Information in Remote Sensing

Spectral mixture analysis: Determines the abundance of materials (e.g. precision agriculture).

Characterization: Determines variability of identified material (e.g. wet/dry sand, soil particle size effects).

Identification: Determines the unique identity of the foregoing generic categories (e.g. land-cover or mineral mapping).

Discrimination: Determines generic categories of the foregoing classes.

Classification: Separates materials into spectrally similar groups (e.g., urban data classification).

Detection: Determines the presence of materials, objects, activities, or events.

Spectral Signature Development

SWIR color composite
from hyperspectral
data cube

The spectral signature of a pixel is a combination of the reflected or emitted energy from all the features that fall within that pixel area.

Concept of hyperspectral imaging using NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory's Airborne Visible Infra-Red Imaging Spectrometer

Demo: concept of hyperspectral imaging

Demo will be performed using ITTVIS Envi 4.5 (<http://www.ittvis.com>)

Presence of mixed pixels in hyperspectral data

Some particularities of hyperspectral data are not to be found in other types of image data:

- *Mixed pixels* (due to insufficient spatial resolution and mixing effects in surfaces)
- *Sub-pixel targets* (very important and crucial in many hyperspectral applications)

Presence of mixed pixels in hyperspectral data

Macroscopic mixture:

15% soil, 25% tree, 60% grass in a 3x3 meter-pixel

Intimate mixture:

Minerals intimately mixed in a 1-meter pixel

Increasing the spatial resolution of the sensor does not necessarily solve the problem!

- *Mixed pixels* can still be obtained at very high spatial resolutions (may complicate analysis)
- *Intimate mixtures* may take place regardless of the spatial resolution available
- Many techniques for hyperspectral imaging do not take into account such phenomena
- In this tutorial, we illustrate different techniques for addressing the mixture problem in hyperspectral data interpretation. This problem can be addressed using different techniques and this tutorial just intends to cover and discuss some of them!

Linear versus nonlinear mixing

- *Linear mixture model*
 - ✓ *Assumes that endmember substances are sitting side-by-side within the FOV.*
- *Nonlinear mixture model*
 - ✓ *Assumes that endmember components are randomly distributed throughout the FOV.*
 - ✓ *Multiple scattering effects.*

Linear versus nonlinear mixing

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 - ✓ Multiple scattering effects.

Linear spectral unmixing (LSU)

- The goal is to find extreme pixel vectors (*endmembers*) that can be used to “**unmix**” other mixed pixels in the data using a *linear mixture model*.
- Each “**mixed**” pixel can be obtained as a combination of endmember *fractional abundances*. A crucial issue is *how to find spectral endmembers*.

Standard linear mixture-based processing chain

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Linear mixture-based processing chain (revisited).-

Endmember extraction algorithms

Endmember extraction algorithms: simultaneous versus sequential

Different approaches depending on the actual **implementation**:

Simultaneous algorithms: they assume that the number of endmembers p is known a priori. For each value of p , they recalculate all the endmembers (they do not take advantage of previously calculated $p-1$ endmembers). Example: N-FINDR.

N-FINDR algorithm

Sequential algorithms: they produce a set of endmembers in sequential order, i.e., if we are searching for p endmembers, a subset of previously calculated $p-1$ endmembers would always be in the final set. Examples: PPI, OSP, VCA.

Pixel Purity Index (PPI)

Pixel Purity Index (PPI) algorithm.-

- Parameters: k (number of skewers) and t (cut-off threshold)
- It is not an iterative algorithm (no convergence criteria)
- No estimation of number of endmembers *a priori*
- Manual intervention required to select a final set of endmembers

ENVI's N-Dimensional visualization tool

Pixel Purity Index (PPI) algorithm.-

Demo: endmember extraction using PPI

Demo will be performed using ITTVIS Envi 4.5 (<http://www.itvis.com>)

Orthogonal Subspace Projection (OSP)

Spectral-based method developed by Harsanyi and Chang (IEEE-TGRS 1994):

1. Select the brightest pixel from the scene as the initial one
2. Apply an orthogonal subspace projection operator to all the pixels in the original image to identify the most orthogonal pixel to the first one (second *endmember*)
3. Apply the orthogonal subspace projector again to all pixels, looking for the most orthogonal one with regards to the first two (third *endmember*)
4. Repeat the process until a predetermined number of *endmembers* is found

Orthogonal subspace projector:

$$P_U^\perp = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{U})^{-1} \mathbf{U}^T$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and \mathbf{U} is a matrix in which the newly extracted pixels (*endmembers*) are incorporated

N-FINDR

Spectral-based method developed by Winter (Proceedings of SPIE, 2003):

1. Dimensional reduction using MNF (ordering resulting components in terms of signal to noise ratio) or PCA (ordering components in terms of variance)

N-FINDR

Spectral-based method developed by Winter (Proceedings of SPIE, 2003):

1. Dimensional reduction using MNF (ordering resulting components in terms of signal to noise ratio) or PCA (ordering components in terms of variance)
2. Random initial selection of endmembers according to a predetermined number
3. Test each pixel in each *endmember* position and retain combinations with *highest volume*

Integrating of spatial and spectral information

- Much effort has been given to extracting endmembers in *spectral* terms.
- Data analysis is carried out without incorporating information about *spatial* context.

- There is a need to incorporate the *image representation* of the data in the analysis.
- Most available approaches consider spatial and spectral information *separately*.
- Several approaches illustrated in this tutorial to achieve the desired integration.

- Mathematical morphology is a nonlinear *spatial-based* technique that provides a framework to achieve the desired *integration* of spatial and spectral data:

Binary erosion.-

Structuring element

- Mathematical morphology is a nonlinear *spatial-based* technique that provides a framework to achieve the desired *integration* of spatial and spectral data:

Binary dilation.-

Greyscale Mathematical Morphology

- *Greyscale* morphology relies on a *partial* ordering relation between image pixels.

- Morphological operations for *hyperspectral imagery* require *ordering* of image *pixels*.
- Two strategies explored in the past: PCA-based ordering and vector-based ordering.

- Opening and closing: shape-preserving operators.
- Excellent filtering properties:

Morphological opening (erosion + dilation)

*Structuring
element*

Spectral angle to measure spectral similarity

Spectral angle mapper:

Does not take into account vector length (amount of reflected radiation), only the intrinsic characteristics of the spectral signature (material composition).

Only spectral distance able to deal with scaling introduced by illumination effects.

Can we use morphology to extract endmembers?

- Morphological operations for *hyperspectral imagery* require *ordering* of image *pixels*.
- Vector ordering relation* is required to avoid introducing *new spectral constituents* in the data.
- Based on a *pointwise* distance function (SAM) and a *cumulative* distance measure.

- The *greatest* element is the *most spectrally distinct (pure)* in the structuring element.
- The *least* element is the *most spectrally similar (mixed)* in the structuring element.

Endmember extraction using extended morphology

- Integration of spectral and **spatial** information (computation intensive)
- Selection of the most *spectrally pure* and the *most spectrally mixed* signatures.

Processing examples:

Original image

False color composition bands: 657, 551 and 496 nm

Multi-channel dilation

Disc SE radius=1 pixel (5 m)

Automatic Morphological Endmember Extraction (AMEE)

Spatial-spectral method developed by Plaza et al. (IEEE-TGRS, 2002)

1. Move a spatial kernel through all the pixels in the input data and calculate the pixel which is most spectrally distinct with regards to the other pixels in the same kernel using a cumulative spectral angle distance (SAD) for *morphological erosion and dilation*
2. Calculate the difference between *erosion* and *dilation* (morphological eccentricity)

Automatic Morphological Endmember Extraction (AMEE)

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2. Calculate the difference between *erosion* and *dilation* (morphological eccentricity)
3. Apply automatic Otsu thresholding method to obtain endmember candidates
4. Extraction of final *endmembers* (the optional region growing step is replaced by the application of the OSP algorithm to obtain spectrally distinct *endmembers*)

Spatial Spectral Endmember Extraction (SSEE)

Spatial-spectral method developed by Rivard et al. (RSE, 2007):

1. Process the image using a *local search window* and apply *singular value decomposition (SVD)* to determine a set of eigenvectors that describe most of the spectral variance in the window.

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2. Projection of the entire image data onto eigenvectors to determine *candidate endmember pixels*
3. Use of spatial constraints to combine and average spectrally similar candidate endmember pixels (preserve similar but distinct endmembers that occupy unique image regions)

Spatial Pre-Processing (SPP).-

Spatial-spectral method developed by Zortea and Plaza (IEEE-TGRS, 2009)

1. Move a spatial kernel around each hyperspectral pixel vector and calculate a spatial correction factor for each pixel

$$\alpha(i, j) = \sum_{r=i-d}^{i+d} \sum_{s=j-d}^{j+d} \beta(r-i, s-j) \cdot \gamma(r-i, s-j)$$

Process that assigns different weights to the pixels in the window (inversely proportional to the squared euclidean distance between the central pixel and each neighbor)

Spectral similarity metric between the central pixel and each pixel in the local neighborhood (in our case, the spectral angle distance)

Spatial Pre-Processing (SPP)

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1. Move a spatial kernel around each hyperspectral pixel vector and calculate a spatial correction factor for each pixel
2. Assign a weight to the spectral signature of each pixel depending on the spectral similarity between each pixel and its spatial neighbors, so that *anomalous pixels* are displaced from the centroid, while spatially *homogeneous* pixels are not displaced

Spatial Pre-Processing (SPP)

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1. Move a spatial kernel around each hyperspectral pixel vector and calculate a spatial correction factor for each pixel
2. Assign a weight to the spectral signature of each pixel depending on the spectral similarity between each pixel and its spatial neighbors, so that *anomalous* pixels are displaced from the centroid, while spatially *homogeneous* pixels are not displaced
3. Apply a spectral-based *endmember extraction* algorithm (such as OSP or N-FINDR) after the preprocessing, obtaining a final set of endmembers.

Region-based spatial preprocessing (RBSPP)

- Transition areas between different land-cover classes are more likely to contain mixed pixels (we assume that pure signatures are more likely to be present in well-defined, spatially homogeneous regions)
- Three design principles:
 1. The inclusion of spatial information is performed as a preprocessing module which uses a region-based approach (**as opposed to SPP**) to reduce the sensitivity to spatial window shapes and sizes
 2. The method uses a region-based approach (**as opposed to SPP**) which better model natural scenes with step discontinuities and multi-scale features and regions
 3. The inclusion of spatial information happens only at the preprocessing stage, and it does not introduce modifications in the spectral-based endmember extraction (**this feature was already available in SPP**)

Flowchart of region-based spatial preprocessing (RBSPP)

Endmember extraction without the pure pixel assumption

- Due to the spatial resolution or the intimate mixtures that happens at any scale maybe the endmembers are not present in the data.
- There are several endmember extraction techniques that solve this problem, assuming that the endmembers are not in the data.

Endmember extraction algorithms: pure pixel assumption

Different approaches according to the **pure pixel assumption**: presence/absence.

Endmember extraction algorithms: pure pixel assumption

Different approaches according to the **pure pixel assumption**: presence/absence

Algorithm

pixels available
pure pixel

Algorithm

generate pure
meaning of

they extract the purest
rest pixels when no
, ...

a: they usually
problem: physical
, ...

Minimum Volume Simplex Analysis (MVSA)

- Tries to find the simplex with minimum volume that contains all pixels.
- MVSA is initialized with an inflated version of the VCA solution.
- MVSA works with the dimensionally reduced version of the data (PCA, MNF,..)

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y &= \underline{MS} \\
 \text{s.t.} & \quad S \succeq 0, \quad \mathbf{1}_p^T S = \mathbf{1}_p^T
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y &\equiv [y_1, \dots, y_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n} & M &\equiv [m_1, \dots, m_p] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p} \\
 & & S &\in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n}
 \end{aligned}$$

Minimum Volume Simplex Analysis (MVSA)

- MVSA solves the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M^* &= \arg \min_M |\det(M)| \\
 \text{s.t. : } & \underline{QY} \succeq 0, \quad \underline{1_p^T QY} = \underline{1_N^T}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$Q \equiv \underline{M^{-1}}$$

$$Y \equiv [y_1, \dots, y_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n} \quad M \equiv [m_1, \dots, m_p] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$$

- Due to the fact that minimum volume algorithms are very sensitive to noise, MVSA runs a final step in which the abundance fraction positivity hard constraint is replaced by a soft constraint.

Simplex Identification via Split Augmented Lagrangian (SISAL)

- In SISAL the positivity constraints are replaced by hinge-type soft constraints.
- Such replacement has three advantages:
 - 1) Robustness to outliers and noise.
 - 2) Robustness to poor initialization
 - 3) Opens the door to deal with large problems.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q}^* &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{Q}} -\log |\det(\mathbf{Q})| \\ \text{s.t. : } & \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{Y} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{1}_p^T \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{a}^T. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q}^* &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{Q}} -\log |\det(\mathbf{Q})| + \lambda \|\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{Y}\|_h \\ \text{s.t. : } & \mathbf{1}_p^T \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{a}^T, \end{aligned}$$

$$\|\mathbf{X}\|_h \equiv \sum_{ij} h([\mathbf{X}]_{ij}) \qquad h(x) \equiv \max\{-x, 0\}$$

Simplex Identification via Split Augmented Lagrangian (SISAL)

- SISAL solves the same optimization problem by a sequence of variable splitting and augmented Lagrangian optimizations.
- The computational complexity of this algorithm is $O(np)$ where n is the number of pixel vectors and p is the number of endmembers.

A new approach: MINVEST

The probability that the observation of a pixel is inside the simplex S is, at most:

$$p_N = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^N.$$

The number of pixels $P = p \times r$ that are located inside the simplex S depends on the distribution of zero abundance values over the pixels. Being r_N the number of pixels that have N zero values, $N=0,1,\dots,n-1$, the number of pixels inside S is, at most:

$$P = \sum_{N=0}^{n-1} r_N p_N.$$

- 1) Estimate the number of interior pixels (ρ).
- 2) Generate starting simplex (provided by N-FINDR in our case).
- 3) While $P > \rho$

3.1) Calculate V according to:

$$\min_V \left\{ f(V) := \det \begin{pmatrix} V \\ \mathbf{1}^T \end{pmatrix} \right\}$$

$$a_k = \begin{pmatrix} V \\ \mathbf{1}^T \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} z_k \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \geq 0, \quad k = 1, \dots, r,$$

3.2) Remove pixels at boundaries

3.3) Recalculate P and repeat from 3.1

Synthetic Image Generation

- The scenes have been generated using fractals to generate *random spatial patterns*
- Each fractal image is divided into a set of classes or *clusters*
- Mixed pixels are generated inside each cluster using library signatures
- Spectral signatures obtained from a *library of mineral spectral signatures* available online from U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) – <http://speclab.cr.usgs.gov>
- Random noise in different signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) is added to the scenes

Fractal 1

Fractal 2

Fractal 3

Fractal 4

Fractal 5

Clusters fractal 1

Clusters fractal 2

Clusters fractal 3

Clusters fractal 4

Clusters fractal 5

Synthetic Image Generation

- Image available: http://www.unex.es/grupos/hypercomp/otros_datos/images

AVIRIS Data Over Cuprite, Nevada

Spectral angle to measure spectral similarity

Spectral angle distance:

Does not take into account vector length (amount of reflected radiation), only the intrinsic characteristics of the spectral signature (material composition).

Only spectral distance able to deal with scaling introduced by illumination effects.

Experiments with Synthetic Images

- Average spectral angle (degrees) between the ground-truth USGS mineral spectra and the endmembers extracted across the five synthetic scenes with different SNRs:

Algorithm	SNR=30:1	SNR=50:1	SNR=70:1	SNR=90:1	SNR=110:1
N-FINDR	2.089	0.463	0.383	0.388	0.361
OSP	2.118	0.452	0.349	0.361	0.345
VCA	2.187	0.520	0.367	0.433	0.435
SPP+N-FINDR	2.293	0.778	0.701	0.694	0.693
SPP+OSP	2.342	0.622	0.536	0.529	0.529
SPP+VCA	2.271	0.455	0.327	0.319	0.347
RBSPP+N-FINDR	2.174	0.874	0.676	0.786	0.804
RBSPP+OSP	2.226	0.764	1.020	1.088	1.034
RBSPP+VCA	1.033	0.685	0.678	0.809	0.714
AMEE	2.670	1.260	0.969	1.193	1.252
SSEE	2.124	1.077	0.576	0.722	0.645

- Average root mean square error after reconstructing the five synthetic scenes (with different SNRs) using the endmembers extracted by several methods:

Algorithm	SNR=30:1	SNR=50:1	SNR=70:1	SNR=90:1	SNR=110:1
N-FINDR	0.356	0.039	0.009	0.007	0.008
OSP	0.359	0.039	0.010	0.008	0.008
VCA	0.369	0.044	0.017	0.021	0.018
SPP+N-FINDR	0.359	0.045	0.017	0.016	0.016
SPP+OSP	0.368	0.048	0.016	0.015	0.015
SPP+VCA	0.368	0.040	0.011	0.009	0.009
RBSPP+N-FINDR	0.358	0.049	0.028	0.026	0.028
RBSPP+OSP	0.359	0.055	0.072	0.054	0.054
RBSPP+VCA	0.308	0.048	0.033	0.043	0.028
AMEE	0.627	0.484	0.468	0.473	0.484
SSEE	0.358	0.135	0.035	0.066	0.026

Experiments with AVIRIS Cuprite Image

- Spectral angle (degrees) between the ground-truth USGS mineral spectra and the endmembers extracted by different algorithms from the AVIRIS Cuprite scene:

Algorithm	Alunite	Budding.	Calcite	Kaolinite	Muscovite	Mean
N-FINDR	4.81	4.29	7.60	9.92	5.05	6.33
OSP	4.81	4.16	9.52	10.76	5.29	6.91
VCA	6.91	5.38	9.53	9.65	6.47	7.59
SPP+N-FINDR	7.72	4.27	9.34	11.26	5.69	7.66
SPP+OSP	6.06	4.27	8.43	12.28	4.64	7.14
SPP+VCA	14.11	8.49	11.94	13.86	5.61	10.80
RBSPP+N-FINDR	7.22	5.71	5.59	10.43	5.08	6.81
RBSPP+OSP	6.86	4.16	10.05	11.14	5.70	7.58
RBSPP+VCA	6.86	4.34	8.31	10.19	5.42	7.02
AMEE	4.81	4.17	5.87	8.74	4.61	5.64
SSEE	4.81	4.16	8.48	10.73	4.63	6.57

- Processing times (seconds) measured in a PC with 2.67 GHz CPU and 4 GB RAM:

Algorithm	Spatial preprocessing	Endmember extraction	Total processing time
N-FINDR	-	466.08	466.08
OSP	-	136.09	136.09
VCA	-	31.12	31.12
SPP+N-FINDR	50.06	466.08	516.14
SPP+OSP	50.06	136.09	186.15
SPP+VCA	50.06	31.12	81.18
RBSPP+N-FINDR	96.51	17.72	114.23
RBSPP+OSP	96.51	5.71	102.22
RBSPP+VCA	96.51	5.89	102.40
AMEE	-	76.06	76.06
SSEE	-	1051.23	1051.23

Overview of Some Available Endmember Extraction Methods

OSP
(0.129)

N-FINDR (0.090)

VCA
(0.081)

AMEE
(0.265)

SPP+OSP
(0.165)

SPP+N-FINDR
(0.043)

SPP+VCA
(0.100)

SSEE
(0.101)

RBSPP+OSP
(0.079)

RBSPP+N-FINDR
(0.100)

RBSPP+VCA
(0.073)

Online tutorial on endmember extraction & unmixing

Pixel Purity Index (PPI)

N-FINDR algorithm

<http://www.hyperinet.eu/event1.html>
Look for “Files practice” including:

- 1) *Matlab code* for all algorithms
- 2) *Simulated* hyperspectral data
- 3) *Real* hyperspectral data
- 4) Step-by-step *practice session*
- 5) *Exercises and questions*

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3. Abundance Estimation

- 3.1. Unconstrained least squares linear unmixing
- 3.2. Nonnegativity constrained least squares linear unmixing
- 3.3. Fully constrained least squares linear unmixing

Unconstrained Abundance Estimation

- When all the endmember information (i.e., the number of endmembers and their spectral signatures) are known, abundances can be estimated via the least squares solution.
- If the two abundance constraints are ignored, abundance estimation is to find $\hat{\alpha}$ such that the pixel reconstruction error:

$$e = \|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{M}\hat{\alpha}\|^2$$

is minimized. The least squares (LS) solution is:

$$\hat{\alpha} = (\mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{r}$$

Nonnegativity Constrained Abundance Estimation

- If the abundance nonnegativity constraint needs to be satisfied, the problem of abundance estimation becomes a constrained optimization problem:

$$\min e = \min f(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{r} - 2\mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{M}\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^T \mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{M}\boldsymbol{\alpha}$$

$$\text{Subject to } 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq 1, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq p$$

- This optimization problem with inequality constraints can be solved by quadratic programming since the objective function is a quadratic function.

Fully Constrained Abundance Estimation

- If both abundance nonnegativity and sum-to-one constraints need to be satisfied, the constrained optimization problem becomes

$$\min e = \min f(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{r} - 2\mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{M}\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^T \mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{M}\boldsymbol{\alpha}$$

$$\text{Subject to : } \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \cdots + \alpha_p = 1$$

$$0 \leq \alpha_i \leq 1, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq p$$

- Actually, the sum-to-one constraint can be easily satisfied by adding a row vector with all elements being one to the endmember matrix \mathbf{M} , adding an element one to the pixel vector \mathbf{r} , and solving the resulting least squares problem:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} \\ \mathbf{1} \end{bmatrix} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{r}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{r}} = \tilde{\mathbf{M}}\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \mathbf{n}$$